

SECTION OF MATHEMATICS, PHYSICS, AND INFORMATICS

USE OF CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

*Abdykerimova E.,
Takenova B.*

*Caspian university of technology and engineering named after Sh.Yessenov
Kazakhstan, Aktau*

Abstract

The article discusses the problem of using the means of information and communication technologies, in particular, cloud technologies in the methodological work of the teacher. The relevance of using the Google tool in the implementation of methodological activities by teachers is justified. We are talking about joint activities between teachers and students, which are very important for modern educational tasks. The didactic capabilities of cloud technologies will be demonstrated. Based on the analysis of information sources, it is indicated which Google tools can be used in the implementation of the teacher's methodological work. The features of the use of cloud technologies made it possible to draw conclusions about their didactic potential.

Keywords: information technology, educational process, cloud technologies, didactic opportunities, methodological activities.

Today, cloud technologies are developing rapidly and cover more areas of activity than ever before. Cloud technology-offers a groundbreaking alternative to traditional learning, creating didactic opportunities for independent learning, interactive lessons and collective learning. In addition, the network cloud allows students to interact and work together with their teachers and peers, regardless of location.

The methodological work of the teacher is a system of interrelated actions based on the achievements of advanced pedagogical experience and specific conditions of educational work, which is aimed at comprehensively improving the qualifications and professional skills of each teacher.

The methodological activity of the teacher is a constant type of activity that contributes to the implementation of planning, compilation, selection and application of teaching aids for a specific discipline, their development and improvement.

Methodological work at the university is divided into four types: scientific and methodological, organizational and methodological, educational and methodological and expert-methodological.

There are two main forms of methodological work - collective and individual-oriented. Collective methodological work is manifested primarily in the active participation of teachers in joint discussion of problems. Individual work allows the teacher to independently study the necessary regulatory and educational documents, plan and organize work on the assimilation of the discipline by students, promptly monitor and adjust the educational process [1].

The studies of the above authors are devoted to the content of some forms of methodological work, but the technological aspects of their implementation are not considered.

Currently, it is impossible not to use modern teaching technologies in the organization of the educational process. The actual task of training and education

can be called the development of professional competencies in students, which are revealed through the formation of skills and qualities of the student: personal responsibility, communicative flexibility, the ability to self-development, the development of thinking, the ability to find information in different forms and in different ways, analyze, manage, combine, evaluate and create.

The listed qualities should be formed not only within the framework of the information and communication technologies course-they are metaspecific. This is stated in the list of requirements for learning outcomes set out in educational standards. From a technological point of view, the implementation of these requirements presupposes the need and availability of the following technologies for students and teachers:

- creation of electronic documents of various formats-text, graphic, video, etc.;
- providing all interested parties with the opportunity to remotely access the creative results of individual and collective work;
- use of internet resources in various aspects of the educational process;
- organization of collective (joint) educational activities of students and teachers.

All of the listed tasks are successfully solved when we turn to cloud technologies for storing and processing information.

Currently, users use Yandex. Disk, Облако@mail.ru, Microsoft OneDrive, Dropbox, Box.net, you can use Google Drive, OpenDrive, etc. Let's look at some examples of using cloud technologies.

Yandex. Disk is a cloud service that allows users to store their data on servers in the «cloud» and transfer them to other users on the internet. If necessary, the user can re-send large documents or access files with a significant number of students. The default limit size of downloadable files is 10 GB of space is recommended,

you can expand 20 GB or more, storage time is unlimited. All files are checked by antivirus, and their transfer is carried out on an encrypted connection. Yandex.Disk in the cloud, files are located not on the same server, but on different servers. This provides high reliability: you can not be afraid that the data will be lost in case of physical damage or hacking of servers. At the moment, user registration is available to everyone.

Yandex.Disk is not only a convenient free file storage space, but also provides a wide range of possibilities for editing them. Upload data to cloud storage, exchange with other users, etc. The service offers the following features:

- takes video and photos from phones and smartphones. This allows you to save memory on mobile devices. All content is loaded in original quality, thanks to the large amount of allocated space, an impressive number of photos and videos can be placed on the disk;

- convenient file exchange up to 50 GB. Allows you to create short links to such files, which provides quick data exchange with other users. You can view the files by links directly in the browser, save them to your hard drive or download them to your computer;

- convenient and fast, stored on the hard drive of a personal computer;

- Free access to the online version of Microsoft Office. This allows users to work with Excel, Word, PowerPoint directly in the browser, without installing programs. If necessary, it is very convenient to quickly edit files or work from mobile devices.

The service includes a screenshot editor and other useful options. Yandex.Disk is constantly developing and adding new features [2].

Облако@mail.ru - allows you to store music, videos, pictures and other files in the cloud and synchronize data on computers, smartphones or tablets and share them with other Internet users. The free storage volume is 8 GB, with the possibility of increasing it to 4 TB for a fee. Work with common packages and online processing of documents, tables and presentations have been implemented in the cloud.

OneDrive allows you to store 5 GB of information for free. It is possible to view images as preliminary sketches, as well as view them as slides. OneDrive has support for Office Online. It allows users to download, create, edit and share Microsoft Office documents directly in a web browser. Users can create, view and edit Word, Excel, PowerPoint and OneNote documents directly in the browser. The advantage is the ability to burn files using a simple drag-and-drop or web application. There is remote access to a computer running Windows. OneDrive supports PDF format and ODF standard. The SkyDrive search function does not support searching for documents in PDF format, but it does support searching in Microsoft Office: doc, docx, ppt, pptx, xls, and xlsx formats. Entire packages can be loaded with a single archive. There is a limit of 4GB and 65,000 files per download.

Dropbox allows users to create a special package (folder) on their computer, which is synchronized with the same content, regardless of what device is used for

viewing. The files hosted in this package are also available through the Dropbox website and mobile apps. Dropbox works on the Freemium model, where users have the opportunity to create a free account with a certain amount of free space, and to increase the size of the account, a paid subscription is required. Dropbox allows you to host files on remote servers using a user-friendly or browser-based web interface. When you install the Dropbox client software on your computer, a synced package is created. Dropbox keeps a download history so that you can recover data after deleting files from the server. Files uploaded via the client have no size limits, but files uploaded via the web interface are limited to 20 GB. For Dropbox Professional and Dropbox Business users, there is Smart Sync functionality to save hard drive space. Offers up to 2GB of free data storage, up to 16GB for free. You can also buy 1 TB.

OpenDrive is a service that provides cloud storage for document viewing, sharing, and collaboration from anywhere, i.e., a cloud drive with 5 GB of free access from anywhere [3].

Google Drive is the ability to store information in the cloud, as well as the advanced tools for its processing are harmoniously combined. Based on Google Drive, the Google Suite for Education environment, specialized for solving educational tasks, was created. But even without it, the competent use of Google Drive allows solving many problems of organizing and supporting the educational process in any educational subject. This, in turn, allows subject teachers to be introduced to the Google Drive tool and the possibilities of using it in the educational process.

Overview of Google Drive features. The main tools that allow the teacher to create his own space online and organize educational activities are: Google Drive, Google Form, Google Documents, Google Tables, Google Calendar, Google Presentations, Google Photos, Gmail Mail, Google Sites.

Google Drive is a virtual storage space of 15 gigabytes. You can save files on this virtual drive or download files from your computer and share them with other users. To allow access to files, there are specific privacy settings that you can change access settings for. Documents are created and stored on disk, but their functionality is not always sufficient to create complex media products, such as mind maps, interactive posters or virtual exhibitions. To solve this problem, it is possible to add various network services to the disk for creating web applications and further convenient access to them. With its help, you can work with documents, tables, presentations, PDF files and forms. Unlike standard software, the Google Drive service allows you to work with various types of files online in real time. In other words, editing and commenting can be done with the simultaneous participation of the teacher and students. In addition, this resource ensures the preservation and availability of tasks, as all changes are automatically saved in the Google cloud after their implementation, which ensures information protection against unexpected interruptions in the operation of software and hardware. The Google Drive app requires a Google account. Google Drive provides storage of files in any format, individual or joint access to them

from any device, as well as the ability to synchronize data stored on several devices.

Google Form is a tool that allows you to conduct various surveys and create surveys, tests. When you open the form, a Google spreadsheet is automatically created. The form is automatically saved to Google Drive with current changes. A ready-made Google form can be distributed through social networks or e-mail. Advantages of Google Forms:

- the possibility of using videos and video materials;
- automatic processing of answers with a visual suggestion in the form of a diagram;
- the possibility of using a personal graphic design of the survey;
- the possibility of posting the form on social networks and sending it to an electronic address;
- the ability to work simultaneously on creating and editing the form of several users.

Google Docs is a tool that has a number of advantages that can be used to teach students:

1. Shared access is the ability of several users to use a document by choosing the right to read, comment or edit it. It is also possible to post the document on social networks and send it by e-mail.
2. Ability to insert various elements - you can insert tables, formulas, pictures, special symbols, links into documents.
3. Comments - teachers and students can leave their comments and suggestions on the content of the document with the possibility of dialogue via e-mail.
4. Add-ons - expand the possibilities of creating and using applications, for example, graphics, voice messages, etc. insertion.
5. Convenient storage - all documents are automatically stored in the cloud, which allows you to access them anywhere with any device that has access to the Internet.

Google Docs includes text documents, tables, presentations, images, and more. allows to do. In terms of functionality, Google documents are inferior to software products such as Microsoft Office and Open Office, but despite this, they support many necessary functions, do not require installation on a computer, because they can be opened through a browser and are ideal for working online. All files are created in Google Drive and saved automatically as you edit them. You can apply different privacy settings to the created files: make them open to all users or give access to individuals. In addition, you can copy the created documents to a computer and open them using Microsoft Office. Google Docs service has all the necessary functionality for creating and editing text documents. It makes working with documents much easier: you can work remotely without downloading documents to a computer. Selective access to a document allows you to work with multiple users on multiple collaborative projects. Text documents can be saved in the following formats: DOC, PDF, etc. Working with formatting tools is easy and does not require additional explanations.

Google Docs allows teachers and students to work remotely on shared documents, projects, and teachers to monitor and manage this work. Google Docs is an

online office that includes full-featured tools for creating text documents, spreadsheets, visual aids, PDF files and presentations, as well as for their collaborative use and publishing on the Internet [4].

Google Sheets - allows you to easily create, share and modify tables on the web, analyze and visualize data, similar to Excel, but with some advantages. Key features of Google Sheets:

- you can import and export .xls, .csv, .txt files and export data to a PDF or HTML file;
- formatting cells and changing formulas, calculating their results and presenting data as needed;
- communicate in real time with other users who change your schedule;
- paste the table or part of it on your blog or website. This service can be used to systematize educational material, then to create diagrams and graphs, to process the results of laboratory work, home research and experiments in various activities.

Google Sheets allows you to create summary tables and charts for data analysis, for example:

- Table-behavior (concept, properties);
- Table-comparison;
- Table of results of laboratory work;
- Table for filling (to confirm formulas, concepts, etc.);
- Table with results of joint research or design work;
- Table-trainer (for quantities, symbols, units of measurement, laws, graphic representations of processes);
- Table-rating;
- Schedule-self-assessment;
- Table-calculation;
- Achievements table.

The teacher only needs to prepare the initial schedule and give students access to it. They can work individually or in small groups: search for information on the Internet and fill in the table. This is possible when creating an annotated directory of educational websites for the class. Thus, the Google table is one of the main and most common types of information presentation.

Google Calendar - Allows users to create events, manage multiple calendars, and share calendars with groups. Users can view a daily, weekly or monthly calendar. The curriculum for students can be formalized in the form of a calendar with several events - classes or events every day.

A teacher can create such a calendar for himself or for groups of students and arrange a notification of any event to his e-mail or SMS on a mobile phone. The calendar helps to optimize all the important tasks and activities, preventing them from accidentally forgetting something and not remembering them.

Google Slides - this can be considered an alternative to PowerPoint, but with limited editing capabilities. Presentations made in individual or joint mode allow to visualize information, save time while studying some topics, learn new information on the subject, teach to work in a group [4].

Google Photos lets you create diagrams, charts, and other types of images.

Gmail (www.gmail.com) is just as popular as Google Mail, a free email service with innovative features such as chain view, a search-oriented interface, and a large amount of disk space. The main advantages of Gmail are:

- allows you to combine several mailboxes with one account;
- files of various formats - text, tabular and graphic documents - are easily attached to the letter;
- there is a search system for key words.

Different «labels» can be assigned to incoming mail. A teacher can have several packages (folders): «letters from students», «letters from colleagues», «ideas for lessons», «work plans», «graphs», etc.

Gmail works harder than any other mail system to protect its users from receiving spam.

Gmail also has an online chat feature. Google Chat lets you send and receive instant messages to friends, family, and colleagues. To speed up the communication with his colleague, the teacher can invite him to Gmail and add him to the chat. In addition, there can be group chats where several people can participate. It allows teachers to work with a specific group on a joint project and topic under consideration online and conduct classes outside the classroom online.

Google sites is a service for creating personal sites that does not require special knowledge of the basics of site creation, so it is accessible and understandable to any user.

For collaborative work, the teacher can create his own website with various materials on the topics covered, interesting facts, links, media products, tests and assignments for students, which they can do using Google Docs and send the results of their work directly to the teacher's site. can, for example, post links to completed tasks with comments or pin them to a specified page on the site. The teacher can also place Google maps on the site pages. Google sites allow placing flash-applications on their pages: virtual tours, laboratories, interactive posters. It is also possible to host teacher assignments and create learning applications, for example, with the help of LearningApps, and they can also be placed on the site. These can be quizzes, word puzzles, tests, creative tasks. You can conduct a dialogue in the comments, solve the questions that arise during the execution of the tasks together. The site also has the ability to create and post useful links. You can use Symbaloo to create such collections.

Researchers have noted that the use of cloud technologies in the educational process has a number of advantages [7]. We offer them in the following groups:

- technical advantages: only access to the Internet is required to organize the educational process, there are no special requirements for the technical characteristics of a computer or other device;
- technological advantages: students do not need to install additional software, it is enough to use any browser and access the Internet;
- economic advantages: most cloud technologies and services are accompanied by a free license;
- methodological advantages: cloud technologies allow students to organize their own and joint work both in class and outside of class (preparation of text

files and presentations, organization of discussion of revision of documents in real time with other students, performance of practical tasks for processing various information objects: processing texts and formatting, creating tables and diagrams in a text editor); exchange of information and documents between students and the teacher: checking completed tasks, advising on tasks and projects).

Cloud services provide access to various educational materials: multimedia, visual, interactive and text.

By comparing the features of the interactive teaching strategy (teacher-student, teacher-student, student-student, student-student interaction) and the capabilities of cloud technologies, we came to a conclusion about their didactic potential in organizing the considered strategy. The main difference between a cloud software solution and a conventional software solution is that all the information that the user works with is not stored on his hard drive, but on a remote server. All types of interaction shown in the cloud service are carried out using any technical devices. Therefore, the teacher, while organizing his own work, should create learning tasks that provide for the optimal combination of activities (work in pairs, groups, small groups).

Let's consider the possibilities of using them in the educational process to organize students' independent work. Using Gmail e-mail allows you to exchange information and documents necessary for the educational process, check students' homework, and give them advice.

An important feature is the ability to perform joint projects in groups. During the execution of tasks, joint preparation of text files, presentations and other documents, discussion of corrections with other students in real time, publication of work results in the form of publicly available web pages, and execution of practical tasks for processing information objects are carried out. This is possible when using Google Docs services (documents and presentations). Google Docs (sheets) allows you to create summary tables and charts for data analysis. Ability to organize online collection of information from many participants of the educational process, to monitor the performance of each task.

Using the Google Docs (forms) service, using special forms in the document, allows you to organize a test with different types of questions, organize a question-and-answer contest, and make a survey for students. This allows for self-monitoring, current, thematic and final monitoring.

Planning the educational process using the Google Calendar service allows you to make a schedule of theoretical and practical lessons, monitor and self-work, remind about submission deadlines, notify about homework and lesson changes.

Focusing on the didactic capabilities of cloud services, we emphasize that they are sufficient and the most optimal (from a technological point of view) for the educational process, namely Microsoft One Drive, Google Classroom and Google Drive clouds. Let's briefly comment on the results of the comparison.

The One Drive service is convenient both for uploading files for independent assignments outside the

classroom and for posting students' completed work. It is useful to use this service even for students who could not attend the training sessions. Students place the completed works in their folders. This service allows you to work with Microsoft Office applications, even if the student does not have this program package on his computer, the student is offered an online version of the program. Working in Word, Excel, PowerPoint, you can save and open files directly from the program to the cloud.

Classroom was created as a Google service, but currently there are many solutions for optimizing work in Google Drive, Google Classroom is ready to provide users with a universal solution by integrating them. Quick integration with Google Drive, a fast interface, and new features teachers need. Additionally, the service has mobile apps available for iOS and Android devices. The apps allow users to create and pin photos, share files from other apps, and interact privately.

Google Drive is convenient to use as part of independent work to create a group project. For example, you can offer students to make an online presentation while studying certain topics. First, a file is created - a layout of the presentation, which the students of the group can access via a link and go to the presentation editor. You don't need to register with Google. Depending on the situation, students work individually or in pairs, and can communicate with each other and the teacher by entering text in the notes field. Another advantage of Google Drive is the ability to conduct polls with tasks. The results are collected in a separate file, the level of mastery of the test questions can be analyzed. Cloud technologies contribute not only to the organization of independent work of students outside the classroom, but also to the formation of general competence.

Using Google Drive, the design service allows you to achieve such goals as analyzing and summarizing data in the educational process, planning and working in a team, working with modern ICT, preparing an article and mastering the skills of speaking with a presentation.

A very important advantage of organizing educational design in an information and communication environment, including using Google Drive, is not only «openness», the ability to see and evaluate everyone's contribution to the collective work due to the common work resource of all students, but also in the team, taking the experience of team members. is to learn design skills through cooperation and interaction of students, students and teachers.

When implementing an educational project using ICT, it is required to have the following services of the information and communication environment:

- placement of various information - documents, links, research sources, content created by students participating in the project in the general resource;
- discussion on design issues;
- formation (editing) of unified documents at different stages of design;
- search for information sources for research activities;
- use of modern means of communication.

The design activity organized in the educational process consisted of several stages:

- preparation and planning;
- collection of materials, placement and research in the common resource;
- creation of collective documents (text, presentations), their protection by students and evaluation of the project by the teacher. The activities of the students and the teacher were implemented in Google Drive at each stage.

The list of teacher's methodological activities can be supplemented, however, the development of the Google tool, thanks to its constant expansion, allows us to say with confidence that teachers will always use it.

With the help of cloud technologies, individual characteristics of students are taken into account, appropriate teaching methods and methods are selected. As a result of working with cloud services, students' independence, ability to plan, and organization develop. Study motivation increases, students can use the organization of study work and skills to work in different situations. Self-monitoring and self-evaluation contribute to the formation of reflection. The ability to reflect will be useful to the student not only in studies, but also in life.

The Google Drive environment offers the teacher wide and convenient tools for the practical implementation of all types of methodological activities. In our opinion, one of the most important is the ability to organize joint activities. For the community of teachers, it is to exchange information, in particular, teaching experience; joint projects - to develop methodologies; allows for discussions and consultations, including consultation with distant colleagues or methodological scholars. Methods of collective and joint work with students, first of all, ensure the activation of their educational activities, and therefore lead to an increase in the effectiveness of the educational process. These considerations make it possible to raise the question of mandatory mastering of Google tools by all teachers in the higher educational institution during methodological training or in the process of professional development.

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